

SHARED VALUES - INFLUENCING BEHAVIOUR IN CROSS CULTURAL TEAMS

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Abstract: When we join an international team, we sometimes encounter people who have different values, assumptions and beliefs from us about how teams should work together and get things done. These differences present both challenges and opportunities for effective cross-cultural team working. Preparing cross-cultural teams to identify and manage potential conflicts due to cultural differences is key to achieving outstanding performance.

Man spends major part of his life in the organisations within which he works. When people join an organisation, they bring with them the unique values and behaviours that they have been taught. Any organisation with firmly established organisational culture would be taught the values, beliefs and expected behaviours of that organisation. Just as society moulds human behaviour, an organisation also moulds human behaviour that is in tune with the prevalent set of norms and behaviour. In this process, certain basic attitudes and beliefs about the people and their work situations are slowly but firmly accepted in the organisation, which becomes its 'Organisational Culture.'

This paper highlights the influence of values on cross-cultural teams and how these values are created in cross-cultural teams.

Key Words: Beliefs, Cross Cultural Teams. Culture, Expatriates, Shared Values, Synergy, Values, Value System, Workforce Diversity

INTRODUCTION

We are living in a time where globalisation is no longer limited to the multinational distribution strategies of very large enterprises. It is now at the core of operations for vast numbers of organisations large and small. Global Teams, Virtual Environments, International Projects and Assignments or Cross-Cultural Management Teams are just a few examples of how

companies respond to global demands to leverage and transfer international know-how. For people working in international or global team environments, challenges are vast. They have to deal with different perceptions, expectations and interpretations of leadership, communication, teamwork, negotiation, and change and knowledge management among their team members. At the root of most of these differences is the complexity of culture and cultural orientations.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

People often talk about how the world is getting 'smaller', thanks to travel and technology. But the reality is that, even though we interact with different cultures more than ever, there are still major differences between countries. People often think differently, conduct business differently, and have different expectations. This makes living in a diverse world so interesting. However, it makes doing business a bit challenging- especially if we're not prepared. What's normal in our country might be a serious mistake elsewhere. When Easterners come to a Western country (like the UK or the US) for the first time, they might be shocked at just how fast things move. A business deal that would take weeks or months in their country might take only a few days in the West. The differences can be substantial, mostly because the ways in which these two regions conduct business are extremely different. In the East, business usually depends on relationships. Entire teams are involved in the decision making process, and things rarely move quickly. In the West, people usually act more as individuals. They might make decisions quickly, and they often don't have to consult their entire team for agreement. They're far more likely to take risks to achieve the things they want.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The present paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To assess the influence of values in cross cultural teams
- To assess the value system of Indian managers
- To assess the importance of values in cross cultural teams.

The rapid ethnic and cultural diversification of the labor force and the expansion of businesses overseas in the recent decades have been reflected by an increasing interest to cross-cultural issues in management. Several papers have offered general overviews of the literature in the field of cross-cultural management. Studies have recognised organisational culture as a potential major barrier to success (Tuggle, 2000). Some, such as McDermott and O'Dell (2001, pp 76-85) have also recommended solutions. The problem with these studies, however, is that it is difficult to determine from them the aspects of organisational culture which, in the first place, would create a barrier to knowledge sharing, especially with global virtual teams. This problem can only be addressed by first developing a sound dimensioning of culture as it affects knowledge sharing in global virtual teams.

Dimensions of organisational culture can be broadly classified as (a) value based and (b) work practice based. Most studies, considered inadequate by Reigle and Westbrook (2000) in their measures for organisational culture, are value based, multilevel, usually small scale and non-comparative (Van den Berg and Wilderom, 2004)

That several studies have demonstrated significant correlation between organisational culture and employee behaviour and attitudes (Kreittner and Kinicki, 2002, p 70) is of great research interest because it spares us the necessity to peel through the layers of culture to get embedded values which experts in culture, anyway, say lie beneath the

threshold of our conscious awareness (Hall, 1976b). In agreement with this view, Hofstede (2003) viewed culture as a construct and therefore is “not directly accessible to observation but inferable from ... behaviours and useful in predicting other ... behaviour” (p 69). Though Park *et al* (2004, p 108) acknowledge the value-based approach to a *deep* study of culture, they also argue that if the goal of a study is to obtain a global perception of an organisation’s culture, a questionnaire using a practice-based approach would be adequate. Thus, for their study, they dimensioned organisational culture into (a) trust, (b) sharing information freely, and (c) working closely with others or developing friends at work. The four items they used were actually from 54 items developed by Block (1978) and later decreased to 44 items by Harper (2000).

The 44 attributes, though useful, are not only too many as a basic dimension of a researchable concept but apparently are also overlapping. For example “confront conflict directly” may overlap with “decisiveness”. One approach to using the list is to handpick some attributes as done by Park *et al* (2004). Perhaps a better approach is to use cluster and factor analysis to endeavour to group and trim these attributes so that we can distill the core dimensions of

organisational culture. Meanwhile, let us investigate how other recent researchers dimension organisational culture.

Based on Kostova’s (1999) definition, Van den Berg and Wilderom (2004) have defined organisational culture in terms of work practices (rather than values). They justify their adoption of work practices using Hofstede’s (2001, p 394) research, which demonstrated that organisations showed more differences in work practices than in values. From analyzing earlier dimensions of organisational culture (Hofstede *et al*, 1990; O’Reilly *et al*, 1991; Gordon and DiTomaso, 1992; Denison and Mishra, 1995; Van Muijen *et al*, 1999), Van den Berg and Wilderom (2004) have derived four dimensions, viz: (a) autonomy, (b) external orientation, (c) inter-departmental coordination, (d) human resource orientation, and (e) improvement orientation.

The known most recent researchers who have worked on dimensioning organisational culture from work-practice approach are Park *et al* (2004) and Van den Berg and Wilderom (2004) whose studies have been presented. If we put their dimensions together, we have the eight dimensions shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Dimensions of Organisational Culture

Inter-departmental coordination	Human resource orientation
Trust	Autonomy
External orientation	Sharing information freely
Improvement orientation	Working closely with others

Rokeach Value Survey

Milton Rokeach created the Rokeach Value Survey (RVS). The RVS consists

of two sets of values with each set containing eighteen individual value items. The RVS is shown in Table 2

Table 2 – Rokeach Value Survey

S. No.	Terminal Values	Instrumental Values
1	A comfortable life (a prosperous life)	Ambitious (hard-working, aspiring)
2	An exciting life (a stimulating, active life)	Broadminded (open-minded)
3	A sense of accomplishment (lasting contribution)	Capable (competent, effective)
4	A world at peace. (free of war and conflict)	Cheerful (light-hearted, joyful)
5	A world of beauty (beauty of nature and the arts)	Clean (neat, tidy)
6	Equality (brotherhood, equal opportunity for all)	Courageous (standing up for your beliefs)
7	Family security (taking care of loved ones)	Forgiving (willing to pardon others)
8	Freedom (independence, free choice)	Helpful (working for the welfare of others)
9	Happiness (contentedness)	Honest (sincere, truthful)
10	Inner harmony (freedom from inner conflict)	Imaginative (daring creative)
11	Mature love (sexual and spiritual intimacy)	Independent (self-reliant, self sufficient)
12	National Security (protection from attack)	Intellectual (intelligent, reflective)
13	Pleasure (an enjoyable, leisurely life)	Logical (consistent, rational)
14	Salvation (saved, eternal life)	Loving (affectionate, tender)
15	Self-respect (self esteem)	Obedient (dutiful, respectful)
16	Social recognition (respect, admiration)	Polite, courteous (well-mannered)
17	True friendship (close companionship)	Responsible (dependable, reliable)
18	Wisdom (a mature understanding of life)	Self-controlled (restrained, self-disciplined)

CULTURE

Culture in general is concerned with beliefs and values on the basis of which

people interpret experiences and behave, individually and in groups. Broadly and simply put, “culture” refers to a group or community with which you share

common experiences that shape the way you understand the world. The same person, thus, can belong to several different cultures depending on his or her birthplace, nationality, education, language, physical condition, ethnicity, family status, age, gender, sexual orientation, religion, place of work, profession and its corporate culture. Culture is the 'lens' through which we view the world. It is central to what we see, how we make sense of what we see, and how we express our self.

Man spends major part of his life in the organisations within which he works. When people join an organisation, they bring with them the unique values and behaviours that they have been taught. Any organisation with firmly established organisational culture would be taught the values, beliefs and expected behaviours of that organisation. Just as society moulds human behaviour, an organisation also moulds human behaviour that is in tune with the prevalent set of norms and behaviour. In this process, certain basic attitudes and beliefs about the people and their work situations are slowly but firmly accepted in the organisation, which becomes its 'Organisational Culture.' Organisational culture comprises the attitudes, experiences, beliefs and values of an organisation. It has been defined as "the specific collection of values and norms that are shared by people and groups in an organisation and that control the way they interact with each other and with stakeholders outside the organisation.

TYPES OF CULTURE

The different types of culture as stated by various researchers are mentioned herein below:

- **Strong culture:** Strong culture is said to exist where staff respond to stimulus because of their alignment to organizational values. A strong culture facilitates coordination and communication and distinguishes successful organisations from others. When culture is strong, people do things because it is the right thing to do, there is a risk of another phenomenon – groupthink.
- **Weak culture:** There is a weak culture where there is little alignment with organisational values and control must be exercised through extensive procedures and bureaucracy.
- **Academy culture:** Employees are highly skilled and tend to stay in the organisation, while working their way up the ranks. The organisation provides a stable environment in which employees can develop and exercise their skills. For instance universities, hospitals, large corporations, etc.
- **Baseball Team Culture:** Employees are 'free agents' who have highly prized skills. They are in high demand and can rather easily get jobs elsewhere. This type of culture exists in fast-paced, high risk organisations, such as investment banking, advertising, etc.
- **Fortress Culture:** Employees don't know if they'll be laid off or not. These organisations often undergo massive reorganization. There are many opportunities for those with timely, specialized skills. For instance savings and loans, large car companies etc.

- **Club culture:** The most important requirement for employees in this culture is to fit into the group. Usually employees start at the bottom and stay with the organisation. The organisation promotes from within and highly values seniority. For instance military, some law firms, etc.
- **Power culture:** Within a power culture, control is the key element. Power cultures are usually found within a small or medium size organisation. Decisions in an organisation that display a power culture are centralized around one key individual. That person likes control and the power behind it. As group work is not evident in a power culture, the organisation can react quickly to dangers around it as no consultation is involved. However this culture has its problems, lack of consultation can lead to staff feeling undervalued and demotivated, motivated which can also lead to high staff turnover.
- **Role culture:** Common in most organisations today is a role culture. In a role culture, organisations are split into various functions and each individual within the function is assigned a particular role. The role culture has the benefit of specialization. Employees focus on their particular role as assigned to them by their job description and this should increase productivity for the company.
- **Task culture:** A task culture refers to a team based approach to complete a particular task. They are popular in today's modern business society where the organisation will establish particular project teams to complete a task to date. A task culture clearly offers some benefits. Staff feels motivated because they are empowered to make decisions within their team, they will also feel valued because they have been selected within that team and given the responsibility to bring the task to a successful end.
- **Person culture:** Person cultures are commonly found in charities or non profit organisations. The focus of the organisation is the individual or a particular aim.

MANAGEMENT SHOULD UNDERSTAND THE ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE

In order to have efficient working of cross cultural teams, the management of an organisation should understand the organisational culture in depth. Proper understanding of organisational culture is required for the following reasons:

- Culture is an asset that can also be a liability. It is an asset as it facilitates better cooperation and communication between management and employees. It is a liability when important shared beliefs and values interfere with the needs of the business and of the company and the people who work for it. Hence,
- An understanding of organisational culture is important in the field of

organisational behaviour as it give proper understanding, insight and feedback to the leaders and management about the present, cultural pattern that facilitate, either to development or constraints to organisational development.

- An understanding of organisational culture is important as it explore the ethos and managerial practices at work, which would go a long way in developing positive attitudes, which in turn are likely to exert positive influence on performance.
- An understanding of organisational culture is important because no organisation can operate in isolation to its cultural environment. In other words, organisations are social systems that must be inevitably operating to survive.
- An understanding of organisational culture is significant as it establishes the linkage between culture, leadership and work ethics in building human and social capital and it is trough human beings that organisations can sustain high performance.

ELEMENTS OF ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE

The various elements of organisational culture may include:

- Stated and unstated values
- Customs and rituals
- Stories and myths about the history of the group

- Overt and implicit expectations for member behaviour
- Metaphors and symbols – may be unconscious but can be found embodied in other cultural elements
- Shop talk – typical language used in and about the group
- Climate – the feelings evoked by the way members interact with each other, with outsiders, and with their environment, including the physical space they occupy.

CROSS-CULTURAL TEAMS

When we join an international team, we sometimes encounter people who have different values, assumptions and beliefs from us about how teams should work together and get things done. These differences present both challenges and opportunities for effective cross-cultural team working. Preparing cross-cultural teams to identify and manage potential conflicts due to cultural differences is key to achieving outstanding performance. When new team members are brought on board, little attention is paid to the orientation of existing team members to the dynamics they will be facing. Both the existing and new team members have challenges that need to be addressed to arrive at practical solutions to cross cultural issues. These can be successfully addressed during new employee orientation by adding a day to the standard orientation that existing team members and managers attend, to examine cultural differences and set working agreements around potential conflicts.

Team members work in increasingly diverse environments: in terms of age (there are older workers), gender (there are more women), race (there are more

people of color), language (there are more languages spoken), and nationality (there are more immigrants). Beyond these differences, there are also deeper cultural differences that influence the way conflict is approached.

CROSS CULTURAL UNDERSTANDING

In order to make cross-cultural global cooperation work, cross-cultural competences must be strengthened. Cultural differences which can be seen, tasted, felt, smelled or heard are not the ones that cause difficulties. It is the invisible cultural differences that create misunderstanding.

Cross-cultural understanding is one of the necessary ingredients in cross-national understanding. Cross-cultural understanding is concerned with understanding people from different cultural backgrounds, in order to be able to do business with them, work with them, or possibly moves to and functions in their countries. Culture finds expression through the patterns of behaviour, decision-making processes, ethics, morals and values on which a society is based. National cultures are built up over many years and spring from a country's history, geography, sociology, religion and language.

WHAT CROSS CULTURAL TEAMS REQUIRED TO DO

Cross cultural teams are required to:

- Develop a shared understanding of what individual team members bring to the team from their diverse cultural backgrounds;

- Develop a shared vocabulary to talk about culture and cultural differences;
- Recognise the potential challenges and opportunities that cultural differences presents to the team
- Understand the competencies associated with cross-culturally effective individuals and teams;
- Develop practical techniques for overcoming cultural and linguistic barriers;
- Put into place strategies to leverage cultural diversity on an ongoing basis;

WHAT INDIVIDUAL MEMBER LEARN IN CROSS CULTURAL TEAM

The individual member in cross cultural team learns as to:

- What culture is, what it looks like, and why it is important;
- What we bring to our new team from our cultural background;
- Culture difference among team members;
- The cultural challenges and opportunities in the team;
- How to implement shared values into the day-to-day work of the team;
- How to leverage culture on an ongoing basis
- How to establish shared team values;

WHAT A GOOD CROSS-CULTURAL TEAM PROVIDES TO AN INDIVIDUAL MEMBER

The good and efficient cross-cultural team provides the following to an individual member of a team:

- A greater understanding of the diversity of values and assumptions within the team environment;
- Improved relationships with other team members;
- Improved confidence in working in a cross cultural team environment;
- An enhanced sense of team identity and goals;
- Strategies for anticipating, recognizing and resolving cultural challenges, both within the team and beyond;

WORKFORCE DIVERSITY – AN OVERVIEW

In the world of human resources, everywhere you turn these days people are talking about diversity in the workforce. In particular, companies that operate globally are aware that to go beyond what is required of them legally and morally in eradicating discrimination can bring about a positive climate that will engage their employees, improve their productivity and enhance the effectiveness of their organisation. The view has long been held that by encouraging applications from candidates across the broad spectrum of age, gender, disability, race, companies can acquire a wide range of knowledge and perspectives and thereby increase their competitive strength on a number of different levels.

Most people refer to workforce diversity as employing people from identity groups that may lack representation in their existing workplace structures, either across the organisation or at departmental level. In certain industries, there are strong logical arguments to encourage diversity in different sections

of the business; for instance, an employee could bring with him 'buy-side' knowledge about a particular demographic group.

There is more to diversity in the workplace than this, however, companies need to start looking at diversity more comprehensively and begin to relate the benefits of an employee's potentially unique perspective to new and creative approaches to working.

REASONS FOR WORKFORCE DIVERSITY

- **Customers have operations in different places:** When customers started setting up their operations in different countries, and they wanted a known company to service their needs there. So companies had set up operations there. Customers were expanding globally and companies had to align their growth with them. So companies set up their operations in different countries and recruiting people there. This is true in case of IT companies.
- **9/11 Disaster:** Another reasons why companies opted to work out of multiple locations and therefore have a diverse workforce was the 9/11 disaster. Companies wondered if they should risk all their assets in one place. There is a need to de-risk themselves from such disasters.

EXPATRIATES IN INDIAN COMPANIES

The Indian job market is full of attractive opportunities, not only for domestic talents but for foreign workforce as well. The number of foreigners seeking jobs in India is increasing every year. Why are expats ready to work in India? What attracts these expatriates fly to India? Some of the reasons that add to the trend of expats looking for more jobs in India are as follows:

- **Growth opportunities:** India, being one of the fastest growing economies in the world, offers a large number of growth opportunities to expats. More expats seek jobs in India on account of job cuts, outsourcing and high taxes in western nations.
- **Adds value to resume:** There are no doubts about how Indian experience adds values to ones resume. It reflects an individual's hard work and ability to adapt and deal with diversity. One gets to know the different cultures, improve networking skills and know to deal with people.
- **Compensation:** The compensation provided by Indian companies maintains external equity and are almost at par with what is being paid in foreign countries. Expats with specialized skills which are unavailable in India, due to financial and technology constraint like molecular research are being offered highly attractive packages attractive positions. Companies are offering attractive leadership positions to experienced expatriates.

- **Unemployment in industrialized economies:** The rate of unemployment is increasing in industrialized economies while the growth opportunities are increasing in South Asian countries. As a result many expats have saturation in their careers in their countries are heading towards Indian markets to grab the opportunities here and move ahead in their careers.

EXAMPLES FROM COMPANIES

Dr. Reddy's: Dr. Reddy's has embraced associates from diverse origins, cultures, ethnicities and academic streams. This has created a strong character that enables the company to realize its full potential. This diversity of over 8000 associates across 40 nationalities chapters the creative and unconventional thinking. The Company believe that by promoting diversity in employment, associates with the best of abilities, thinking and experience come together on a single platform, creating a powerful workforce that can achieve remarkable results.

HSBC: In the words of HSBC Bank, "We believe that the most important competitive differentiators are the quality of individual service we provide to our customers and the way we treat our employees. Diversity focuses on valuing the differences between people, including customers and staff. We are the world's local bank, a global organisation that understands our local populations and values the diversity of the markets that we operate in. Having a workforce that reflects the composition of the local communities we serve places

us in a strong position to understand and respond to our local customers. Diversity can be regarded as a competitive differentiator, both in employment and in customer markets. Diversity is therefore central to HSBC's brand image and connects with Managing for Growth and our people strategy. Though in India having a formal diversity policy is not a legal requirement, we have formed a committee to drive home this philosophy and have set benchmarks for ourselves towards achieving the stated objectives.”

IBM: As an international company with local management, IBM addresses diversity issues that are representative of local priorities and experience. Issues vary across regions, as well as from country to country. For instance, in Europe, Latin America, the Middle East and Africa, IBM’s policies and practices are mindful of gender, people with disabilities and the growing awareness of ethnic minorities. In Asia Pacific countries, IBM is putting increased focus on issues related to gender, disability and respecting and valuing differences among countries and regions.

Infosys: Infosys announced an intake of 300 graduates from universities in the US in 2006 and about 25 from universities in the UK in 2007 as part of its commitment to create a diversified workforce. The new employees will develop their engineering skills at Infosys Development Centres across India for six months before returning to Infosys offices in the US.

TCS: TCS encourages people from different cultures to work together in project teams, and understand each other better. It also encourages non-Indians to work in India, so that they can better

understand Indian ways of working. It conducts cultural awareness programmes, including an annual event called the Global Village, to facilitate greater sensitivity to other cultures.

VALUES

Values are convictions and a framework of philosophy of an individual on the basis of which he judges what is good or bad, desirable or undesirable, ethical or unethical. Rokeach, a noted socio-psychologist, has defined values as “global beliefs that guide actions and judgements across a variety of situations”. He further says that, *Values represent basic convictions that a specific mode of conduct (or end-state of existence) is personally or socially preferable to an opposite mode of conduct (or end-state of existence).* Values are tinged with moral flavour, involving an individual’s judgement of what is right, good or desirable. Thus values:

- Provide standards of competence and morality;
- Transcend specific objects, situations or persons;
- Are relatively permanent and resistant to change, and
- Are most central to the core of a person.

CLASSIFICATION OF VALUES

Researchers on cultural aspects of human behaviour have classified personal values in different ways.

Table 3 – Classification of Values

CLASSIFICATION		
Allport's classification	Economic	Attach importance to what is useful
	Theoretic	Involve themselves in the use of rational, critical and empirical processes
	Political	Place great emphasis on power
	Social	Attach importance to love and affection. Care for the interests of others and are sympathetic to them.
	Aesthetic	Put emphasis on artistic values and harmony.
	Religious	Attach more importance to unity.
Graves's classification	Existentialism	Orientation of behaviour congruent with existing realities.
	Conformistic	Orientation towards achievement of material beliefs through control over physical resources
	Sociocentric	Orientation with getting people
	Tribalistic	Orientation towards safety by submitting to power
	Egocentric	Orientation to survival and power
England's classification	Pragmatic	Takes a pragmatic view of the situation which is stereotyped; opts for concepts and actions which appear to a person as important and successful irrespective of good or bad
	Moralist	Guided by the ethical consideration of right or wrong, just or unjust, honest or dishonest.
Rokeach's classification	Terminal (end) values	Reflect what a person is ultimately striving to achieve, e.g. comfortable life, family security achievement, self respect, etc.
	Instrumental (means) values	Relates to means for achieving desired ends, e.g. ambition, courage, honesty, imagination, etc.

CREATING VALUES IN CROSS CULTURAL TEAMS

When cross cultural guidance is provided to employees companies should begin by making the participants aware of the fact that their own

behaviour is very much culturally determined. The behaviour, fundamental value system and morals they see as normal will often appear strange to people from other countries. A certain insight into one's own culture is an important prerequisite for understanding

other cultures. The organisation has to see the specific cultural area with in which the employees must function. Patterns of behaviour should be looked upon and also an attempt should be made to provide a historical, geographical, religious and sociological perspective, to make it easier to understand what lies behind the culture. If people from many cultures are required to work together, companies often allow them to create new cultures via group exercises, and thereby provide them with a platform which, over time, will enable the group to develop a group culture based on cultural tolerance.

Values vary across cultures and environments. Societal culture has a strong bearing on value systems. For example, the sanctity of contracts differs across countries. In some countries the idea of merit includes a high component of loyalty; in some others, loyalty doesn't count for much. In some countries doing business with relations and friends is not acceptable; in other places, personal associations count for a lot. Oriental values are in many respects different from those of the West. Anglo-Saxon values differ markedly from the European.

IMPORTANCE OF VALUES IN CROSS CULTURAL TEAMS

Values are important in cross cultural teams because they lay the foundation for understanding attitudes and motivation. The importance of values in cross cultural teams is highlighted below:

- Personal value systems influence a manager's perception of situations;

- Personal value systems influence the way in which a manager views other individuals and groups of individuals;
- Personal value systems influence a manager's decisions and solutions to problems.
- Personal value systems influence the perception of the individual.

VALUES INFLUENCE THE BEHAVIOUR OF PEOPLE

Behaviour of people is influenced by the values which they hold, particularly in terms of those stimuli which have some value orientations. Values influence the behaviour of individuals in the following manner:

- Individuals set limit for the determination of what is ethical or unethical behaviour for themselves as well as for others.
- Individual's perception about the problems he faces and consequently the decisions he makes to overcome those problems are influenced by values. Even value system to top management also influence the choice of organizational goals and strategies adopted to achieve those goals.
- Interpersonal relationships are also influenced by values. How individual looks at other individuals and groups of individuals. Values serve the basis of such interpersonal interactions.
- On the basis of value systems, individuals judge organisational success as well as its achievement. Thus for some individuals organisational success mean something while

for other individuals it means different thing.

- Values also determine the extent to which individuals accept organisational pressures and goals. If these do not match with the values held by them, they thwart the organisational pressures and goals and even leave the organisation.

ESTABLISHING VALUES

In creating the organisational culture, the establishment of values is the first step, which governs the members of the organisation. Values of an organisation are created by those who establish the organisation and in one way; organisational values depend on the values of the founders and other key personnel who are responsible for managing the organisation. These values decide to a very great extent what business; the organisation should be in. values also determine how organisational activities will be carried out, i.e. what type of practices will be followed. Peters and Waterman have described what types of values are followed by excellent companies. These are mentioned herein below:

- A belief in being the best;
- A belief in the importance of the details of execution;
- A belief in the importance of informality to enhance communication;
- A belief in and recognition of the importance of economic growth and profits;
- A belief in superior quality and service;

- A belief that most members of the organisation should be innovative;
- A belief in the importance of people as individuals;

OPERATIONALISING VALUES

Values can not be put into action unless and until they are operationalised. Until operationalising these remain just the thinking of those who have created these. The organisation can undertake the following activities to put value in action:

- The organisation should design its structure that facilitates employees to take those actions that have been envisaged by values.
- The organisation should prepare a written statement containing its values and communicates these to the members of the organisation.
- While selecting the employees, organisation should take care that their values match organisational values. It is desirable to hire those whose values match those of the organisation.
- Various organisational processes should be prescribed in such a way that these inspire employees to adhere to organisational values.
- Reward system should be instituted in the organisation which encourages employees to engage in behaviours that are compatible with organisational values.

VALUE SYSTEM OF INDIAN MANAGERS

Various researchers have attempted to identify the value systems of Indian managers. These are mentioned herein below:

- According to Allport, Graves, England managers tend to have orientation towards economic, theoretic, political, social, aesthetic and religious in that order. Managerial values tend to be existential, conformistic, manipulative, sociocentric, tribalistic and egocentric. Indian managers are more pragmatist than moralist.
- There are generally some acceptable unethical practices in business. Such practices are in the form of nepotism, bribes, gifts, personal favours, unfair competitive practices, dishonesty to customer relations and personal benefits.
- Indian managers give importance to various occupational values in the order of:
 - *To be free from supervision,
 - *Adventurous experiences/challenges,
 - *Social status and prestige,
 - *To exercise leadership and control over others,
 - *Opportunities to work with people,
 - *Chances to earn a good deal of money, and
 - *Stable and secure future
- In terms of work values, Indian managers tend to:
 - *Be money oriented during early days of their career and later shift to matters like job satisfaction, and finally at the end of the

career, to intangible value like status

*Attach high importance to values like loyalty and obedience; and

*Be ambitious, though not overwhelmingly, believe to a large extent in the fate without allowing this belief to directly interfere in doing day-to-day working.

VALUES AND CORPORATE CULTURE

Corporate culture is the term used to describe a system of shared values and beliefs that create behavioural norms to guide the activities of organisational members. It is believed that strong corporate culture facilitates higher performance. Thomas J. Peters and Robert H. Waterman, Jr. authors of *In Search of Excellence* state, for example: "Every excellent company we studied is clear on what it stands for, and takes the process of value shaping seriously".

As a system of shared values, the corporate culture reflects a climate within which people value the same things and apply these values to benefit the corporation as a whole. One example is the dominant value of customer service. This value shall help to keep everyone from top management down to persons on the factory floor pulling in the same direction. Corporate values may be put in the form of slogans such as "The Family Feeling" by an Airline or "Quality at a good price" by a Pharmaceutical giant. The strength of such slogans in communicating values lies in the basic premise that values can influence behaviour. To the extent employees understand and share

corporate values, their behaviour should be more uniform and consistent. The performance of individuals, groups and the organisation as a whole will increase and benefit all. The managers who sense compatibility between their personal values and those of the organisation experience feelings of success in their lives, show high regard for organisational objectives and significant stakeholders, and have a healthy assessment of the values and ethics of their colleagues, subordinates and bosses.

Big organisations develop different cultures which have different performance implications. Organisations with strong cultures that fit the needs and challenges of the situations survive and grow while organisations with weak cultures are phased out. That is why, the study of corporate culture is important in the field of organisational behaviour. It may be noted that corporate culture and its companion notion of 'shared values' are not static concepts. They could be changed or modified to meet the need of changing environment.

CREATING CROSS CULTURAL SYNERGY

Synergy is the creation of something that is greater than the sum of its parts. In other words, a team working well together is more effective than a collection of individuals. Synergy means to make more by combining the individual members of a team than you have when they are separate. Cosmopolitan project team members are capable of creating synergy, ethnocentric ones are not. The benefits of a team approach are well understood in western cultures, though responses to team

behaviour vary considerably throughout the world depending on the specific cultural values held. Incorporating other team members often requires new and different skills from the team leader, often an order of magnitude more difficult than team building with a group all from the same culture.

CONCLUSION

Individuals join the teams with variant motivations, experiences, and values. These natural individual differences tend to direct behavior in numerous, often divergent directions. An understanding of value expectancy of members in a cross cultural team is fundamental to the understanding of managing team culture and behaviour. The value orientation of employees underlies employees and employers behaviour. Major managerial functions and roles are perceived through value driven approaches. Knowledge of culture of a cross cultural team may help us to understand the power of culture on human behaviour at work. It helps in better decision making and control of human behaviour at work.

Culture is a form of organisational knowledge, and should not be viewed as a source of difference and antagonism. Culture should be treated as an object of knowledge management. There is no difference in goal values of those who are formally exposed to some management education programmes and those who are not exposed to such programmes. It is observed that socio-psychological factors such as one's parental background, the contents of one's experience determined by age and nature of group role, seem to go with occupational goal values. The quality and content of our management

education system have to be looked upon from this point of view. At present, it seems that they offer more in terms of techniques rather than the transmission of values.

Effective use of cross cultural teams can provide a source of experience and innovative thinking to enhance the competitive position of organizations. However, cultural differences can interfere with the successful completion of projects in today's multicultural global business community. To achieve the goals and avoid cultural misunderstandings, the managers of cross cultural teams should be culturally sensitive and promote creativity and motivation through flexible leadership. What is clear is that having a diverse culture within an organization does not ensure that a company will improve its effectiveness in researching, developing or commercializing new products in the global market place. It is how the organisation organizes this diverse workforce that will harness the advantages they bring. Leadership and management must create values and cultivate a working climate in which it is acceptable for people from diverse backgrounds to contribute their ideas and contest current practice.

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